

Simultaneous stripping voltammetric determination of zinc, cadmium, thallium and copper ions in different buffer medium as electrolyte

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Abstract : Ga-67, Tl-201 and In-111 radio-nuclides are produced in AMIRS cyclotron by ^{68}Zn (p, 2n) ^{67}Ga , ^{203}Tl (p, 3n) ^{201}Tl and ^{111}Cd (p, n) ^{111}In or ^{112}Cd (p, 2n) ^{111}In reactions respectively. In this method, Zn-68, Tl-203 and Cd-111 or Cd-112 targets (coated on Cu backing) are irradiated. There are amounts of Cu in solution after washing the irradiated targets. Therefore, the presence of copper must also be assayed in quality control steps.

Therefore, simultaneous measurements of Tl, Zn, Cd and Cu could optimize quality control time. Measurements of these elements were performed in different systems and pHs. NaCl 1% solution, NaCl 1% solution and EDTA 0.05 M, NaCl 1% and buffer pH 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 were used in this work.

The highest polarographic currents have been observed for Cu, Cd and Zn in NaCl 1% solution and for Tl in NaCl 1% and EDTA 0.05 M. Therefore the best results were expected with NaCl 1% solution. Detection limits of 0.54, 5.4, 1.5 and 0.4 μg for Cu, Tl, Cd, and Zn were obtained, respectively. Obtained relative standard deviation (RSD) for Cu, Tl, Cd, and Zn, were 29.9, 26.18, 10.1 and 46.97, respectively.

Keywords : Simultaneous polarography, cyclotron production, radio nuclides, buffer medium.

Introduction

Ga-67 is a radio-nuclide with electron capture mode of decay (half-life 78 h, with 185 and 300 keV gamma) that are mainly produced by cyclotron bombardment of enriched Zn-68 target electroplated on natural copper. The ^{67}Ga -citrate complex is one of the most important radio pharmaceuticals in nuclear medicine for tumors imaging¹⁻⁴.

Tl-201 is a potentially useful radio-nuclide for various medical applications. ^{203}Tl is irradiated by a beam of protons (28 MeV) to produce ^{201}Tl by the ^{203}Tl (p, 3n) $^{201}\text{Pb} \rightarrow ^{201}\text{Tl}$ reaction.

In-111 by its suitable characteristics ($T_{1/2}$: 2.8 days, EC, γ -emission), absence of β -emission and low γ -emission of 171 keV (89%) and 254 keV (94%) is well suited for diagnostic nuclear medicine^{6,7}. ^{111}In has been resulted by irradiation of ^{111}Cd at 16 MeV or ^{112}Cd at 27 MeV with proton beam⁴.

Many articles about determination of heavy metals like Tl and transition elements such as Cu, Zn and Cd, have been reported in literature⁸⁻¹¹. van Staden *et al.* used differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetry (DPASV) in a flow system for the simultaneous determination of Cu, Cd, Fe, Pb and Zn. They believed for simultaneous determination of several elements in a single voltammogram it was necessary to find suitable electrolytes. The properties of the supporting electrolyte used in the carrier solution significantly influence the stripping process through redox reactions, formation of complex compounds and of poorly soluble compounds readily adsorbing on the electrode surface and frits used in the cells¹¹.

The simultaneous polarographic determination of Zn, Cd, Tl and Cu in many buffer media as electrolytes was reported in this article. The effect of various pHs was studied in detail to establish conditions which would render their simultaneous determination possibility.

Experimental

Apparatus :

METROHM 757 Polarograph (Switzerland), with a hanging mercury electrode (HMDE) and a saturated calomel electrode as a reference electrode was applied for the measurements. The solutions were initially bubbled for 5 min with nitrogen for the elimination of dissolved oxygen. Polarographic determination of Cd, Zn, Tl and Cu was carried out at 25 ± 0.1 °C. The reference electrode was connected through a KCl-agar bridge. The pH measurements were performed with a line operated Mettler Toledo pH meter.

Materials and reagents :

Stock solution of copper, cadmium, zinc and thallium ions were purchased from Merck (1000 ppm). The working standard solutions were prepared daily by suitable dilution of those stock solutions. High grade nitrogen was used for deaeration of samples and, solvents during analysis.

Buffer solutions were used in this experiment, are buffer pH 2.2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 which were prepared in chemical laboratory as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Buffers used in the experiments

Buffer	Na ₂ HPO ₄ (0.2 N)	Citric acid (0.3 N)	Total (ml)
pH 2.2	1 ml	49 ml	50
pH 4	18.5 ml	31.5 ml	50
pH 6	31 ml	19 ml	50
pH 8	48 ml	2 ml	50
pH 10	0.37 g KCl + 0.31 g	H ₃ BO ₃ + 0.176 g	NaOH dissolved in 100 ml water

All other chemical materials were analytical grade and used without further purification. These materials were purchased from Merck.

Procedure :

Determination of Zn, Cd, Tl and Cu concentration was carried out by differential pulse polarography. Measurements were taken by the triple standard addition method. The electrolyte solution (10 ml) with buffer solution (1 ml) was introduced to the polarographic vessel and bubbled for 5 min for removal of dissolved oxygen. Then polarogram was recorded as a blank. Afterwards standard solution was added for three times and polaro-

gram was recorded each time. Finally, total polarographic curves were recorded.

We have considered qualitative and quantitative analysis of these ions. The operating parameters of differential pulse polarography measurements are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Instrument operating parameters for the analysis of Zn, Cd, Tl and Cu

Parameter	Description
Working electrode	Hanging mercury dropping electrode (HMDE)
Mode	Differential pulse, DP
Blank purge time (s)	300
Purge time before each measurement (s)	10
Deposition potential (V)	-1.20
Deposition time (s)	60
Pulse amplitude (V)	0.05
Start potential (V)	-1.20
End potential (V)	-0.05
No. of replication	2
Sweep rate (V/s)	0.03

Results and discussion

A plot of the current vs potential in a polarography experiment shows the current oscillations corresponding to the drops of Hg falling from the capillary. The limiting current (the plateau on the sigmoid), is called the diffusion current because diffusion is the principal contribution to the flux of electro-active material at this point of the Hg drop life.

The potential of a polarographic indicator electrode at the point, on the rising part of a polarographic wave, where the difference between the total current and the residual current is equal to one-half of the limiting current.

The main difficulty associated with the simultaneous determination of several ions in a single polarogram is preparation of sample solutions. For this purpose, it was necessary to find suitable electrolytes. The properties of the supporting electrolyte used in the carrier solution significantly influence the stripping process through red-ox reactions.

The polarograms of simultaneous determination of Cu, Tl, Cd and Zn, have been shown in Fig. 1. The horizon-

tal axis shows the applied potential and the vertical axis shows the generated polarographic current. Concentration of the studied elements is 11.34 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (0.0162, 0.005, 0.0092 and 0.0157 mol L^{-1} for Cu, Tl, Cd and Zn, respectively).

The highest polarographic current and suitable distance between each peak potential determine appropriate electrolyte. The peak potentials of investigated ions and polarographic currents in different supporting electrolytes are shown in Table 3.

Fig. 1. Polarograms of Cu, Tl, Cd and Zn in NaCl 1% (A), NaCl 1% and EDTA 0.05 M (B), NaCl 1% and buffer pH 2.2 (C), NaCl 1% and buffer pH 4 (D), NaCl 1% and buffer pH 6 (E), NaCl 1% and buffer pH 8 (F), NaCl 1% and buffer pH 10 (G), five replications in NaCl 1% (H).

Table 3. Peaks potential of the ions using different electrolyte solutions

Electrolyte	Cu		Tl		Cd		Zn	
	P.P. ^a	P.C. ^b	P.P.	P.C.	P.P.	P.C.	P.P.	P.C.
NaCl 1%	-0.134	177	-0.468	13.5	-0.612	102.5	-1.004	173.5
NaCl 1% + EDTA 0.05 M	-0.26	158	-0.468	16.7	-0.695	5.9	No peak	-
NaCl 1% + buffer 2.2	-0.135	115.2	-0.464	11	-0.605	80	-0.998	64.2
NaCl 1% + buffer 4	-0.135	57.5	-0.462	13.8	-0.617	66.8	-1.024	56.7
NaCl 1% + buffer 6	-0.136	88.5	-0.468	12.6	-0.623	71.3	-1.024	47.3
NaCl 1% + buffer 8	-0.135	84.5	-0.468	12.65	-0.626	76.5	-1.028	55.2
NaCl 1% + buffer 10	-0.135	103	-0.462	12.9	-0.609	81	-1.015	48

^aPeak potential (V). ^bMax. polarographic current (nA).

An Ep difference of at least 100 mV is desirable to enable adequate separation for simultaneous measurement. Peak potential for Cu and Cd varies from -0.07 to -0.26 V and -0.58 to -0.69 V in different electrolytes respectively while peak potential for Tl and Zn has little movement in different electrolytes (nearly -0.46 and -1 V respectively). Distance between each peak potential (ΔE) is suitable for the simultaneous determination of each ion in all measurements.

The highest polarographic currents for Cu, Cd and Zn (177, 102.5 and 173.5 nA respectively) in NaCl 1% solution and 16.7 nA for Tl in NaCl 1% and EDTA 0.05 M as electrolyte have been observed. *R*-squared value (R^2) for determination of these ions in all electrolytes

(Measurements with the three various concentrations and repeated twice), are shown in Table 4. Approximately, in all determination, great linear relationship between polarographic currents and concentration of ions can be observed except for one case is that illustrated in Table 4. Peak is not observed for Zn when EDTA is electrolyte. This problem might be due to complex formation between Zn and EDTA.

Detection limit and RSD :

To evaluate the proposed system, some analytical parameters such as linear range and detection limits were determined. The detection limits, the minimum concentration of analyte that can be detected at a known confidence level, were calculated from the calibration slopes.

Table 4. R-squared value (R^2) for determination of these ions

Electrolyte	R^2			
	Cu	Tl	Cd	Zn
NaCl 1%	0.9972	0.9999	0.9998	0.9983
NaCl 1% + EDTA 0.05 M	0.9987	0.9999	0.9995	No peak
NaCl 1% + buffer 2.2	0.9979	0.9996	1	0.9997
NaCl 1% + buffer 4	0.9774	0.9995	0.9999	0.9988
NaCl 1% + buffer 6	0.9997	0.9998	0.9998	0.9993
NaCl 1% + buffer 8	0.9999	1	0.9998	0.9997
NaCl 1% + buffer 10	0.9973	1	1	0.9992

The detection limits for Cu, Tl, Cd and Zn were 0.54, 5.4, 1.5 and 0.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ respectively.

The detection limits and linear range can be improved by increasing the deposition time, mercury drop size and pulse amplitude.

The proposed method was repeated for 5 times. A polarogram of solution containing all studied elements is shown in Fig. 1(H). Relative standard deviations for Cu, Tl, Cd and Zn (with parameters in Table 2) are 11.35, 23.76, 9.09 and 39.1 ppt respectively.

Conclusions

The simultaneous polarographic determination of Zn, Cd, Tl and Cu, was performed in many buffer media as electrolytes. The highest polarographic currents for Cu, Cd and Zn (177, 102.5 and 173.5 nA respectively) in

NaCl 1% solution and 16.7 nA for Tl in NaCl 1% and EDTA 0.05 M as electrolyte have been observed. Detection limits for Cu, Cd, Pb and Zn are 0.54, 5.4, 1.5 and 0.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and RSD are 11.35, 23.76, 9.09 and 39.1 ppt respectively. The relative standard deviations values demonstrated the reliability of using the proposed system for simultaneous heavy metal monitoring in water samples.

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